

DETERMINANTS OF FOREIGN RESERVES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the determinants of Nigeria's foreign reserves from 1990 to 2024, addressing persistent concerns over the limited effectiveness of key macroeconomic variables in influencing reserve accumulation. This study specifically examines the impact of the exchange rate (EXR), oil price (OP), and interest rate (INT) on foreign reserves. Employing an ex-post facto research design and the ARDL framework; and data sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Bank Development Indicators, the findings reveal that the exchange rate has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on foreign reserves. Oil price exhibits a negative and insignificant relationship with reserves, while interest rate also shows a negative and insignificant influence. The study concludes that during the period under review, exchange rate movements, oil price fluctuations, and interest rate adjustments did not significantly influence Nigeria's foreign reserves. These results highlight the need for improved exchange rate management, better fiscal discipline in oil revenue utilization, and policies to attract stable capital inflows, thereby providing useful insights for policymakers and enriching the empirical literature on reserve dynamics in emerging economies.¹

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Adequacy of foreign exchange reserves is a key component of good macroeconomic management. It can be used to smooth random and temporary balance of payments (BOP) shocks, maintain exchange rate parity, avoid the macroeconomic costs of adjustment to temporary shocks, and smooth the adjustment of the macroeconomic impact of some permanent shocks (IMF, 1993). Foreign exchange reserves can also be used to smooth exchange rate volatility in illiquid foreign exchange markets. Foreign reserves represent a country's stock of foreign currency assets held by the central bank and serve as a buffer to shield the domestic economy from external shocks and stabilize the exchange rate. Adequate reserves provide the monetary authority with the capacity to intervene in the foreign exchange market during periods of volatility, either by supplying foreign currency to ease pressure or by signalling credibility to markets (Obadan, 2017; IMF, 2016). In line with this principle, the

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has historically used foreign reserves to support the naira through interventions and policy adjustments. Nigeria's economy has been characterized by persistent exchange rate volatility, particularly over the past decade, presenting significant challenges for macroeconomic stability, business operations, and economic growth. External reserves serve as a critical buffer against such volatility, providing the central bank with the necessary ammunition to defend the currency and maintain stability in the foreign exchange market. However, the effectiveness of external reserves in dampening exchange rate fluctuations in Nigeria remains a subject of debate. While periods of reserve accumulation have coincided with relative currency stability, episodes of reserve depletion – often due to falling oil prices or rising external obligations – have intensified exchange rate pressures (Olayungbo & Akinbobola, 2019). Additionally, concerns persist about the optimal level of reserves needed to effectively manage exchange rate risks, especially in the face of competing fiscal demands and declining foreign exchange inflows.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In theory, external reserves serve as a critical policy buffer for supporting economic growth. Adequate reserves enhance macroeconomic stability, strengthen investor confidence, and provide the fiscal and monetary authorities—principally the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)—with the capacity to absorb external shocks and smooth economic fluctuations (Obadan, 2017). However, despite periods of relatively high external reserves, Nigeria's experience suggests that economic growth has remained fragile and uneven, raising questions about the adequacy and effectiveness of reserves in stimulating sustainable growth. According to Akamobi and Ugwunna (2017), foreign reserves have suffered massive depreciation. With the balance of payments in deficit and the naira under pressure, investors are once more cautious than ever. The Central Bank of Nigeria shows that the nation's foreign reserves stood at US\$38.61 billion as of December 2024 but fell to US\$36.21 billion as of December 2025 (Business Day, 2026). This pace of reserve accumulation occurs without regard to diminishing marginal benefits and rising marginal costs. This has led to a debate on the factors determining reserves accumulation. Although many factors have been said to be the determinant of Nigeria's foreign reserves, inconsistencies abound from so many conflicting results. Hence, the essence of this study is to complement existing studies and then ascertain the main determinants of Nigeria's foreign reserves.

1.3 Study Objectives

This study examines the determinants of foreign reserves in Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To evaluate the impact of the exchange rate on foreign reserves in Nigeria.
2. To examine the effect of oil prices on foreign reserves in Nigeria.
3. To analyze the relationship between Nigeria's interest rate and foreign reserves in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following questions are posed to guide the findings of this study.

1. What is the impact of the exchange rate on foreign reserves in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of oil prices on foreign reserves in Nigeria?
3. Does the interest rate have any significant relationship with foreign reserves in Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are presented in their null forms (H_0):

1. H_{01} : Exchange rate does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.
2. H_{02} : Oil price does not have any significant effect on foreign reserves in Nigeria.
3. H_{03} : Interest rate has no significant relationship with foreign reserves in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant both theoretically and practically, particularly within the context of Nigeria's persistent exchange rate volatility, external sector vulnerability, and macroeconomic instability. First, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on the determinants of foreign exchange reserves in developing economies. While several studies have examined the adequacy of reserves globally, empirical evidence for Nigeria remains fragmented and often inconsistent. By systematically identifying and analyzing the key macroeconomic determinants of foreign reserves in Nigeria, this study provides updated and context-specific evidence that enriches the existing literature and clarifies conflicting findings.

Second, the study is significant to monetary authorities, particularly the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Understanding the major drivers of foreign reserves accumulation and depletion is essential for designing effective reserve management strategies. Since external reserves serve as a policy tool for exchange rate stabilization and external shock absorption, insights from this study will assist policymakers in formulating evidence-based foreign exchange and intervention policies that enhance macroeconomic stability.

Third, the study provides useful guidance for fiscal authorities and economic planners. Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil earnings exposes reserves to commodity price volatility. By identifying structural and macroeconomic factors influencing reserves dynamics, the study highlights areas requiring diversification and fiscal discipline, thereby supporting long-term economic sustainability.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is within the period 1990–2024 (35 years), reflecting the objectives of the study and dataset. This study is particularly important in the wake of the Federal Government of Nigeria's policy on a floating exchange rate, which is a departure from the traditional managed exchange rate regime that had been the norm. This study considers foreign reserves, exchange rate, oil price, and interest rate as variables of interest. Data for the study shall be collated annually from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and World Bank publications.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature Review

2.1.1 External and Foreign Reserves

External reserves (also known as foreign exchange reserves or international reserves) refer to a country's holdings of foreign currencies, gold, Special Drawing Rights (SDRs), and reserve positions in the International Monetary Fund (IMF). These reserves are primarily held by central banks and monetary authorities to stabilize the national currency, facilitate international trade and payments, provide liquidity during economic crises, and maintain confidence in the financial system (IMF, 2001; Obstfeld, Shambaugh, & Taylor, 2010).

2.1.2 Foreign Reserves and Economic Growth

External reserves play a pivotal role in Nigeria's economic stability, particularly in relation to economic growth. External reserves consist of foreign currencies, gold, and other assets held by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) for international payments, macroeconomic stabilization, and crisis management (Ijokoh, 2024; Ikwaugu & Eze, 2019). These reserves act as a buffer against external economic shocks, support foreign trade, and enhance investor confidence, all of which are essential for sustained economic growth. Conversely, economic growth refers to a sustained increase in the productive capacity and output of the Nigerian economy over time (Adams & Uchenna, 2024). Weak or unstable growth can deter investment, exacerbate unemployment, and reduce economic predictability.

Although external reserves are crucial for supporting economic growth in Nigeria, their adequacy, timely accumulation, and prudent utilization remain recurring policy challenges. Effective reserves management,

alongside economic diversification and well-coordinated monetary policies, is essential for fostering macroeconomic stability and long-term growth resilience. Numerous studies have examined the relationship between external reserves and economic performance. According to Obadan (2017), adequate external reserves enhance macroeconomic stability and create an enabling environment for economic growth by strengthening policy credibility. Olayungbo and Akinbobola (2019) argued that Nigeria's external reserves contribute significantly to economic growth by cushioning the economy against external shocks. Similarly, Bakare and Fawehinmi (2022) observed that external reserves have a positive effect on economic growth, particularly during oil windfalls, though this effect weakens when reserves fall below a critical threshold.

2.1.3 Exchange Rate and Foreign Reserves

The exchange rate is one of the most critical determinants of external reserves dynamics, particularly in developing and import-dependent economies such as Nigeria (Umar & Gubareva, 2022; IMF, 2023). External reserves are often used by central banks to intervene in the foreign exchange market to stabilize the domestic currency. When exchange rate pressures intensify—especially during periods of currency depreciation—the monetary authority may draw down reserves to defend the currency (Adebayo & Akinsola, 2022). Conversely, exchange rate appreciation or relative stability may support reserves accumulation by reducing the need for persistent intervention and improving capital inflows (World Bank, 2024). The relationship between the exchange rate and external reserves is therefore bidirectional. On one hand, adequate reserves strengthen the credibility of exchange rate management by enabling sustained intervention and anchoring market expectations (IMF, 2023). On the other hand, persistent exchange rate misalignment, speculative attacks, or structural foreign exchange shortages can deplete reserves rapidly, particularly under managed exchange rate regimes such as Nigeria's (CBN, 2023; Umar & Gubareva, 2022). In such regimes, exchange rate volatility often triggers significant reserve movements. Therefore, exchange rate stability is both a determinant and an outcome of reserve adequacy.

Empirical literature suggests that exchange rate depreciation increases the demand for foreign currency and speculative hedging behavior, thereby exerting downward pressure on reserves (Adebayo & Akinsola, 2022). However, when exchange rate reforms improve market transparency, reduce arbitrage, and attract portfolio and foreign direct investment inflows, reserves may improve (IMF, 2023). Thus, the exchange rate–reserve nexus depends largely on the exchange rate regime, capital mobility, and the credibility of monetary policy.

2.1.6 Oil Price and Foreign Reserves

Oil price is a fundamental determinant of external reserves in oil-exporting economies such as Nigeria (Olayungbo & Akinbobola, 2019; World Bank, 2024). Given that crude oil exports account for a substantial proportion of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings, fluctuations in global oil prices directly influence the level of external reserves (IMF, 2023). During periods of high oil prices, export revenues increase significantly, leading to reserves accumulation, improved balance of payments positions, and enhanced exchange rate stability (CBN, 2023). Conversely, oil price collapses reduce foreign exchange inflows, weaken the current account balance, and trigger reserves depletion, as witnessed during the COVID-19 oil price shock (IMF, 2022). However, the oil price–reserves relationship is not purely mechanical. Fiscal behavior and savings discipline play crucial roles. If oil windfalls are excessively spent rather than saved, reserves may not increase proportionately (NEITI, 2024). Furthermore, subsidy payments, rising external debt servicing obligations, and capital outflows may offset oil revenue gains (World Bank, 2024). Thus, while oil price movements are a primary driver of Nigeria's external reserves, the ultimate impact depends on fiscal management, sovereign wealth savings mechanisms, and macroeconomic policy coordination (IMF, 2023).

2.1.7 Interest Rate and Foreign Reserves

The interest rate influences external reserves through capital flow dynamics and monetary policy transmission mechanisms (Umar et al., 2021; IMF, 2023). Higher domestic interest rates can attract foreign portfolio investment by offering better returns on financial assets, thereby increasing foreign exchange inflows and supporting reserves accumulation (Adebayo & Odugbesan, 2021). Conversely, lower interest rates may reduce foreign investor appetite, potentially leading to capital outflows and reserve pressure (World Bank, 2024). In addition, interest rate differentials between Nigeria and advanced economies influence short-term capital movements, which can significantly affect reserves levels, particularly in financially open economies (IMF, 2023).

However, excessive reliance on high interest rates to attract capital inflows may generate adverse domestic consequences, including higher borrowing costs, reduced private investment, and slower economic growth (Adebayo & Odugbesan, 2021). Moreover, volatile portfolio inflows driven by interest rate incentives may be short-lived, exposing reserves to sudden reversals and capital flight risks (Umar et al., 2021). Therefore, the interest rate–reserve relationship is mediated by capital mobility, investor confidence, and the broader macroeconomic environment. Sustainable reserves accumulation requires stable macroeconomic fundamentals rather than short-term monetary tightening strategies.

2.2 Theoretical Literature Review

2.2.1 External Reserve Buffer Stock Model

The buffer stock model first propounded by Robert Heller (1966) treats international reserves exactly like a firm's inventory: a stock that cushions ("buffers") random external payment shocks so the country can keep financing imports, servicing debt, and stabilising its exchange rate without abruptly imposing painful macroeconomic adjustments (devaluation, capital controls, demand compression). According to Heller (1966), central banks hold reserves not only for transaction purposes but also to cushion against external shocks and maintain currency stability. The model supports the view that external reserves act as a "buffer stock" that can be used to absorb volatility in the exchange rate, especially in import-dependent economies such as Nigeria. The buffer stock model remains a benchmark for thinking about reserves: it supplies a transparent rule linking optimal holdings to volatility, opportunity cost, and adjustment penalties. Yet modern reserve accumulation—especially for countries such as Nigeria with oil-linked revenues and financial market exposure—cannot be fully understood without adding precautionary, developmental, and mercantilist layers to this classic inventory framework.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Nwagu, Edeh, and Onoriode (2023) examined the effect of external reserves on economic growth in Nigeria using the E-GARCH (Exponential GARCH) model. The results from the variance equation revealed a statistically insignificant relationship, indicating that changes in external reserves did not exert a significant impact on economic growth during the period under review.

Similarly, Fapetu, Oluwole, Olokoyo, Olabisi, and Owoeye (2023) investigated the relationship between external reserves and economic growth in Nigeria from 1994 to 2019 using secondary data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The study concluded that external reserves exhibited a negative but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth, suggesting that reserve accumulation, largely driven by defensive stabilization motives, did not translate into meaningful growth outcomes over the study period.

Sanusi et al. (2019) examined the factors influencing foreign exchange reserves in South African countries. They employed the autoregressive distributive lags (ARDL) approach to analyze the data. The variables employed in their analysis encompassed foreign reserves, capital inflows, exports, inflation, exchange rates, and

imports. Based on the empirical findings, it has been determined that exports, inflation, exchange rate, and imports exhibit statistical significance. Furthermore, it has been observed that exports, inflation, and exchange rate exert a positive influence on the foreign reserves of South African nations, whereas imports are associated with a negative impact on foreign reserves. Capital inflows exhibit a positive correlation, albeit not a statistically significant one.

Akamobi and Ugwunna (2017) analyzed the determinants of Nigeria’s foreign reserves for the period 1970–2013. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, and the Ordinary Least Squares technique was employed for the analysis. The results revealed that oil price and domestic credit are the major determinants of foreign reserves. Other variables such as domestic income, price level, interest rate, and exchange rate can also be considered determinants of foreign reserves, but only in the long run. Furthermore, the Granger causality test revealed a unidirectional relationship between oil price and foreign reserves. Among others, we recommend that the Nigerian government should encourage other sources of foreign reserves apart from oil to minimize the effect of oil price volatility on foreign reserves as well as on the economy.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Design

This study uses time-series secondary data and the ex-post facto methodology in order to quantify the relationship or effect between the dependent and explanatory variables. The explanatory variables in this study are the exchange rate, oil price, and interest rate, whereas the dependent variable is economic growth. The theoretical threshold of the study anchors on the external reserve buffer stock model. According to Heller (1966), central banks hold reserves not only for transaction purposes but also to cushion against external shocks and maintain currency stability. The model supports the view that external reserves act as a "buffer stock" that can be used to absorb volatility in the exchange rate, thereby stabilizing economic growth, especially in import-dependent economies such as Nigeria.

3.2 Sources of Data

The data for this study were sourced from the publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Bank publications.

3.3 Model Specifications

The model for this study is built to establish the functional and causal relationship between the determinants of External Reserves in Nigeria from 1990 to 2023. In line with the objectives of this study, the model takes the multiple regression structural form below:

$$LNFR_t = f(EXR_t, OP_t, INT_t) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

The functional model of equation (1) was modified into econometric form such that:

$$LNFR_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 EXR_t + \beta_2 OP_t + \beta_3 INT_t + \mu_t \quad (3.2)$$

Furthermore, the natural logarithm of the economic growth rate was used to curtail the effects of a spurious regression. Thus:

$$LNFR_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 EXR_t + \beta_2 OP_t + \beta_3 INT_t + \mu_t \quad (3.3)$$

Where:

LNFR = log of foreign reserves (dependent variable)

EXR = exchange rate

OP = oil price

INT = interest rate

μ_t = error term

α_0 = Intercept of the model

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Structural parameters of the model estimated

LN = natural logarithm

3.4 Unit root test

To fully explore the data generation process, we first examined the time series properties of model variables using the Augmented Dickey- Fuller and Phillips-Perron tests.

The ADF test regression equation with constant is:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k a_j \Delta Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

where Δ is the first difference operator, ε_t is random error term, k = no of lagged differences Y = the dependent variable. The unit root test is then carried out under the null hypothesis $\alpha = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis

of $\alpha < 0$. Once a value for the test statistics $ADF_t = \frac{\hat{\alpha}}{SE(\alpha)} \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$ is computed, we shall compare

it with the relevant critical values for the Dickey-Fuller Test. If the test statistics is greater (in absolute values) than the critical value at 5% or 1% level of significance, then the null hypothesis of $\alpha = 0$ is rejected and no unit root is present. If the variables are non-stationary at level form and integrated of the same order, this implies evidence of co-integration in the model.

3.5 Data Evaluation Method

This study adopts the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) econometric model. The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) is an econometric technique used to estimate long-run relationships in a cointegrated system.

Auto Regressive Distributed Lag

Furthermore, the work set out to present an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model.

$$LNFR_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta FR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta OP + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta INT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i LNFR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i OP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i INT_{t-i} + \phi ECT + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$$

$$ECT_t = Y_t - \alpha_0 - \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_1 \Delta Y_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} \text{ and } \phi = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_1 \Delta Y_{t-i} \dots \dots \dots (3.6)$$

Where

The bound test procedure used equations 3.6 and 3.7 in 3.8 as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = - \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \gamma_1 Y * \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} - \rho Y_{t-1} - \alpha - \sum_{i=0}^p \delta X_{t-i} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3.7)$$

Then we test the existence of a level relationship as $\rho = 0$ and $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = 0$

where Δ = difference operator, α = the short-term coefficient, β = the long run coefficients μ = white noise error term.

3.6 Model Justification

The use of ARDL test approach is predicated on its several advantages over other cointegration tests such as Engle-Granger and Johansen's cointegration method. Firstly, the ARDL efficiently determines the cointegrating

relation in small sample cases (Ghatak & Siddiki, 2001; Tang, 2003), whereas Johansen's method requires large sample for validity. Secondly, other methods requires that the variables must be integrated of the same order before the cointegration test is carried out, while the ARDL approach can be applied irrespective of whether the regressors are I(1) and I(0) or mutually cointegrated, in which the dependent variable must be I(1).

3.7 Significance Test

The significance was tested at the 5% level of significance using the coefficients of the independent variables, following the rule: reject the null hypothesis if the t-prob is less than 0.05; otherwise, accept the null hypothesis when the t-prob is greater than 0.05 (i.e., reject if t-prob < 0.05, accept if t-prob > 0.05).

3.8 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using the probability of the F-statistics: reject the null hypothesis if the probability of the F-statistics is less than the critical value (0.05); otherwise, accept the null hypothesis when the critical value (0.05) exceeds the probability of the F-statistics.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1: Data for Foreign Reserves, Exchange Rate, Oil Price and Interest Rate in Nigeria (1990-2024)

YEAR	Log of the Foreign Reserves	Exchange Rate in Percentage	Oil Price	Interest Rate as a Percentage
1990	2.084492	8.038285	22.36	17.5
1991	2.293544	9.909492	21.39	15
1992	2.850707	17.29843	20.78	21
1993	3.094219	22.0654	18.73	26.9
1994	3.091043	21.996	17.21	12.5
1995	3.086487	21.89526	18.25	12.5
1996	3.085573	21.88443	21.95	12.25
1997	3.08603	21.88605	20.64	12
1998	3.08603	21.886	14.14	12.95083
1999	4.525477	92.3381	17.21	17
2000	4.622027	101.6973	18.25	12
2001	4.7116	111.2313	21.95	12.95083
2002	4.792313	120.5782	20.64	18.88
2003	4.861516	129.2224	14.14	15.02
2004	4.889522	132.888	17.63	14.21
2005	4.877256	131.2743	66.84	6.995
2006	4.857096	128.6517	75.57	10
2007	4.834773	125.8081	104.98	9.5
2008	4.775504	118.5667	61.46	9.75
2009	5.003141	148.88	79.42	6
2010	5.012633	150.2975	112.2	6.25
2011	5.036043	153.8625	113.46	12
2012	5.059426	157.5	113.46	12
2013	5.058218	157.3117	111.13	12
2014	5.06607	158.5526	104.52	13
2015	5.259784	192.4403	54.7	11

2016	5.535324	253.492	42.5	14
2017	5.722899	305.7901	53.11	14
2018	5.726587	306.0837	72.91	14
2019	5.726587	306.921	65.3	13.5
2020	5.882793	358.8108	43.4	11.5
2021	5.994335	401.152	68.86	11.5
2022	6.054392	425.9792	103.19	16.5
2023	6.801717	645.1941	85.4	18.75
2024	7.215643	1478.965	82.94	19.84

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Development Indicator 2025

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Unit Root Test Result

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test is summarized in the Table 4.2 below. This test was carried out on each of the variables at 5% critical value.

Table 4.2: Summary of the Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF Test statistics		Decision	Order of Integration
	At Level	1 st Difference		
LNFR	-0.766368	-5.121944	Stationary at 1st difference	I(1)
EXR	1.172855	6.510840	Stationary at 1st difference	I(1)
OP	-1.616102	-5.527103	Stationary at 1 st difference	I(1)
INT	-2.992752		Stationary at Level	I(0)

Source: Researchers' Computation using E-Views 13 (2026)

The unit root test above reveals that Foreign Reserves (LNFR), Exchange Rate (EXR) and Oil Price (OP) were all stationary at first difference and are said to be integrated of order one I(1). However, Interest Rate (INT) was stationary at level I(0). The decision is based on the fact the ADF statistics that is greater than the ADF critical values at 5%, we reject H_0 and conclude that the variables are stationary. Since the variables are integrated of order one and zero and none of the variables is integrated of order two. We therefore, apply the ARDL bound co-integration test.

4.2.2 ARDL Bound Co-integration Test

A necessary condition for testing for ARDL bound co-integrating test is that each of the variables be integrated of either of order one or zero or both (Pesaran, Shin and Smith, 2001). Since all the variables are integrated of order one and zero, we proceeded to estimate the ARDL bound test. The null hypothesis of ARDL bound co-integration is that the variables are not cointegrated as against the alternative that they are cointegrated. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the F-statistics is greater than the upper bound critical values at chosen level of significance.

Table 4.3: ARDL Bound Co-integration (5% critical value) Test Result for the models

Model	F-Statistics	K	Significance level	Critical Bound Value	
				10 (Lower Bound)	11 (Upper Bound)
	3.8862	3	5%	2.79	3.67

Source: Author’s Computation 2026

From table 4.3 the F-statistics for the model is 3.8862 and is greater than the upper (I1) bound of 3.67 at 5% level of significance. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a long run relationship between the determinants of external reserves in Nigeria. Since there is a long run relationship, we therefore estimate the short run and long run ARDL analysis.

4.2.3 Test for Short Run Relationship

Having ascertained that there exist a co-integrating relationship between external reserves and economic growth in Nigeria, the short run relationship needs to be ascertained.

Table 4.4: Summary of Parsimonious Short Run Relationship Result Between External Reserves and its Determinants in Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Probability
CointEq(-)	-0.124277	0.027319	-4.549024	0.0002

From table 4.4 above; the coefficient of the error correction term (cointEQ) is statistically significant and carries the expected negative sign at 5% level of significant; revealing that a short run relationship exists between the determinants of foreign reserve in Nigeria. The speed of adjustment is -0.124277 that is 12.4% of the adjustment to equilibrium is expected to occur in short run.

4.2.4 Test for Long Run Relationship

It’s imperative to ascertain the long run relationship that exists between the determinants of external reserves in Nigeria.

Table 4.5: Summary of Long Run Relationship between the determinants of external reserves in Nigeria Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	0.014527	0.009114	1.594021	0.1283
OP	-0.031380	0.041186	-0.761920	0.4560
INT	-0.351250	0.353920	-0.992455	0.3341
C	10.42241	7.311374	1.425506	0.1711

Source: Author’s Computation 2026

4.2.5 Interpretation of Long Run ARDL Result

$$LNFR = 10.42241 + 0.014527EXR - 0.031380OP - 0.351250INT$$

The long run coefficient from table 4.5 above shows that the joint impact of all exogenous variables (EXR, OP and INT) on the endogenous variable will amount to 10.42% percent; this is on the basis that they are all held at constant. In other word if all the exogenous variables are held at constant it will amount to 10.42% contribution to foreign reserves in Nigeria.

Exchange Rate (EXR) possessed a positive relationship with foreign reserves in Nigeria with coefficient value of **0.014527 percent**; this entailing that on the long run, as Exchange Rate (EXR) increases by one percent, it causes a **0.014 percent** increase in foreign reserve in Nigeria.

Oil Price (OP) possessed a negative relationship with foreign reserves in Nigeria with coefficient value of **-0.031380 percent**; this entailing that on the long run, as Oil Price (OP) increases by one percent, it causes a **-0.031380 percent** decrease in foreign reserve in Nigeria.

Interest Rate (INT) possessed a negative relationship with foreign reserves in Nigeria with coefficient value of **-0.351250** percent; this entailing that on the long run, as Interest Rate (INT) increases by one percent, it causes a **--0.351250** percent decrease in foreign reserve in Nigeria.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The individual test was carried out to test for joint significance of the independent variables on the dependent variable at 5% level using t-probability and t-statistic shown in table 4.5 and 4.6. The rule applied was: If t-probability is greater than the prescribed level of 5% or 0.05, accept the null hypothesis, otherwise reject the null hypothesis when f-probability is less than 0.05.

H₀₁: Exchange Rate does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

Conclusion: From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of **EXR** was 0.1283, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that Exchange Rate does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Oil Price does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

Conclusion: From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of **OP** was 0.4560, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that Oil Price does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Interest Rate does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

Conclusion: From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of **INT** was 0.3341, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that Interest Rate does not significantly affect foreign reserves in Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of the Findings

This study examined the determinants of foreign reserves in Nigeria from 1990 to 2024, focusing specifically on the exchange rate (EXR), oil price (OP), and interest rate (INT). Based on the empirical results obtained from the ARDL long-run estimation presented in Table 4.5, the following findings emerged in the course of this research:

The estimation results reveal that the exchange rate (EXR) has a positive but statistically insignificant impact on foreign reserves in Nigeria. Specifically, a 1% increase in the exchange rate leads to approximately a 0.014527% increase in foreign reserves in the long run. However, the probability value (0.1283) indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant at the 5% confidence level. Accordingly, although exchange rate movements may influence foreign reserves, the effect is not strong enough to be considered a decisive determinant within the study period. The positive sign implies that depreciation of the naira may be associated with nominal increases in reserves, possibly due to valuation effects or temporary inflows following exchange rate adjustments. Nevertheless, the insignificance indicates that exchange rate policy alone does not substantially determine reserve accumulation in Nigeria. This outcome can be attributed to Nigeria's managed exchange rate regime and structural foreign exchange constraints, where reserves are often used defensively rather than accumulated systematically.

Conversely, the oil price (OP) exhibits a negative and statistically insignificant relationship with foreign reserves. The long-run coefficient of -0.031380 indicates that a 1% increase in oil price leads to a 0.031380% decrease in foreign reserves. This result appears counterintuitive, given Nigeria's heavy dependence on oil

exports as a major source of foreign exchange earnings. The negative sign means that increases in oil prices do not automatically translate into reserves accumulation.

Similarly, the interest rate (INT) shows a negative and statistically insignificant effect on foreign reserves in Nigeria. The coefficient of -0.351250 implies that a 1% increase in the interest rate leads to a 0.351250% decrease in foreign reserves in the long run. The negative relationship indicates that higher interest rates may not necessarily attract sufficient foreign capital inflows to boost reserves. Instead, rising interest rates may reflect macroeconomic instability, inflationary pressures, or tight monetary policy conditions that discourage productive investment and capital inflows. Additionally, interest rate adjustments in Nigeria may not be strong enough to offset external vulnerabilities or exchange rate pressures. The probability value of 0.3341 confirms that the interest rate does not significantly influence foreign reserves within the period under investigation.

The error correction term (ECM) from the short-run analysis is negative and statistically significant (-0.124277), indicating the presence of a stable long-run relationship among the variables. The coefficient shows that approximately 12.4% of short-run disequilibrium is corrected annually towards the long-run equilibrium path. This relatively slow speed of adjustment means that shocks to foreign reserves take time to be absorbed within the Nigerian economy.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Findings

This study investigated the determinants of foreign reserves in Nigeria from 1990 to 2024. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was adopted for data analysis. The following points summarize the findings of the study:

- The exchange rate showed a positive but insignificant effect on Nigeria's external reserves.
- Oil price exhibited a negative and insignificant relationship with Nigeria's external reserves.
- The interest rate had a negative and insignificant influence on Nigeria's external reserves.

5.2 Conclusion

This study examined the long-run impact of selected macroeconomic variables—exchange rate, oil price, and interest rate—on Nigeria's foreign reserves from 1990 to 2024, using the ARDL technique. Secondary data obtained from the publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Bank were utilized. The empirical results revealed that the exchange rate had a positive but statistically insignificant impact on foreign reserves. Oil price and interest rate also emerged as statistically insignificant in explaining variations in foreign reserves within the study period. The study therefore concluded that, during the period covered, exchange rate movements, oil price fluctuations, and interest rate adjustments did not exert a significant influence on foreign reserves accumulation in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

In view of these findings, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. Enhancing Exchange Rate Management Policies: Given that the exchange rate showed a positive but statistically insignificant impact on foreign reserves, policymakers should focus on strengthening exchange rate management strategies. This could involve adopting measures to stabilize the naira and reduce speculative pressures in the foreign exchange market. Additionally, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should consider policies that encourage productive foreign inflows and deter excessive short-term capital outflows, ensuring that exchange rate adjustments translate more effectively into reserve accumulation.

2. Improve Oil Revenue use and Fiscal Discipline: Since oil price had a negative and insignificant effect on foreign reserves, the government should strengthen mechanisms to channel oil revenue into foreign reserves rather than immediate expenditures. This may include enhancing the sovereign wealth fund framework,

improving fiscal discipline, and ensuring that windfalls from oil price increases are partly saved or invested in reserve-enhancing instruments. Better management of oil revenues can help mitigate the weak link observed between oil price fluctuations and reserves accumulation.

3. Adopting Policies to Attract Stable Capital Flows: The negative and insignificant effect of interest rates on foreign reserves indicates that current monetary policy adjustments are insufficient to attract foreign capital effectively. Policymakers should implement strategies to attract long-term and stable capital inflows, such as promoting investment-friendly policies, ensuring macroeconomic stability, and offering incentives for foreign portfolio and direct investments. This approach can help enhance foreign reserves without relying solely on short-term interest rate adjustments.

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